

An empirical case and ongoing efforts on Transversal Computer Strategies & Services for Scientific and Training efforts for the LASF4RI ¹

Thematic areas

- Instrumentation and Computing
- Capacity Building

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Abstract

This white paper outlines a strategic proposal to enhance open-access and free-tier scientific computing and educational resources, leveraging advanced data handling, analysis, and cloud computing technologies. Building on previous work, this proposal updates the 2020 initiatives and presents the state-of-the-art in ongoing projects, such as the deployment of cloud-based HPC resources in Latin American universities. We propose a cohesive strategy to deploy multi-user platforms for scientific data analysis, particularly in resource-limited settings, utilising open data from high-energy physics experiments and other high-dimensional datasets. By strategically using commercial clouds and repositories, we aim to significantly boost computing power access for our researchers and students, preparing them for competitive careers in the industry while democratising access to cutting-edge research tools and methodologies.

¹ The **LASF4RI** is calling a renewed or updated input on the whitepapers of 2019-2020 for large scientific infrastructures among countries in Latin America (<https://lasf4ri.org>)

This approach integrates Software as a Service (SaaS) and Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) solutions to further enhance accessibility and scalability. Additionally, we actively engage in small-scale computing projects and infrastructure-related training programs to build local capacity and foster scientific collaboration across Latin America. Through these efforts, we seek to create a robust, scalable, and accessible framework that supports scientific endeavours and capacity-building projects in the region. Lastly, we advocate for a more focused, task-oriented approach to scientific collaboration that leverages our students' and academics' adaptability and resourcefulness. Rather than replicating large-scale infrastructures typical of more resource-rich countries, we focus on maximising return on investment and fostering regional human capital development.

Introduction

Scientific Computing (SC) and Informatics Technology (IT) are pivotal in modern scientific research and education, offering significant benefits in reproducibility, collaboration, and accessibility. This white paper proposes implementing transversal computer-related strategies and services to support scientific and educational efforts, particularly in regions like Latin America where resources may be limited. Profiting of more than 10 years of expertise in large experimental facilities and open-access projects worldwide, this proposal provides a comprehensive update on past initiatives and current activities.

We aim to inform the scientific community about the latest tools and methodologies needed for experimental and collaborative research. We aim to create virtual spaces where researchers and funding agencies can access reliable, updated information on SC services and tools. This includes data acquisition, transmission, storage, analysis systems, software development, CI/CD practices, and results visualisation.

Training programs are integral and designed to equip research teams with essential skills in documentation, protocol development, and data management. We also highlight the importance of assigning DOIs and licenses and the role of external advisors in enriching the research process.

This white paper presents a dedicated review of scenarios and proposals under the umbrella of a “SC+IT Hub,” showcasing the effective use of hybrid spaces that integrate industrial and academic resources. It includes updates on ongoing activities, small-scale computing projects, infrastructure initiatives, and training programs to build local capacity and foster scientific collaboration across Latin America.

Furthermore, we are building strong and young communities and involving more industrial partners in multiple training and puntual scientific events. The ongoing plan is to keep the engage private industry, relevant NGOs (such as Creative Commons chapters).

Also, the introduction of AI models (like LLMs in scientific production), **dedicated computing resources, IaC and cloud to generate labs that will be integrated into classrooms and curricula.** These efforts already create robust, scalable, and accessible frameworks that support scientific endeavours and capacity-building projects, enhancing the chances that Latin American researchers can fully participate in and contribute to the global scientific community.

Figure 1 provides a simplified overview of multiple experiments and how they access services and tools in the domains of SC and IT. It highlights the typical scenario where independent experiments procure their computing resources, data management systems, analysis tools, and publication platforms independently and uncoordinated. This approach often leads to redundancy and increased costs due to the duplication of services and equipment across different projects.

Figure 1: A simplified view of multiple experiments and how they access services and tools in the areas of Scientific Computing (SC) and Informatics Technology (IT).

Background and Context

Review of Previous Proposals

In the 2019 white paper, “**A Proposal for Transversal Computer-related Strategies & Services for Scientific and Training Efforts for the LASF4RI**”, I identified the need for integrated computer-related strategies to enhance scientific and educational initiatives in Latin America. The proposal emphasised the development and deployment of standardised services and protocols to support the entire lifecycle of scientific experiments—from design and development to deployment, distribution, training, and dissemination of data.

In our 2021 paper, “**A Proposal for Open Access Data and Tools Multi-User Deployment Using ATLAS Open Data for Education**”, we explored the potential of using multi-cloud strategies, encompassing both SaaS and IaaS, to facilitate the deployment of analysis pipelines across diverse computational ecosystems. This approach aimed to replicate sophisticated computing environments in resource-limited settings such as small universities and start-ups, thereby democratising access to advanced research tools previously out of reach for many.

Unlike the 2020 initiative, which focused primarily on infrastructure deployment, **this proposal integrates advanced cloud strategies to ensure scalability and cost efficiency.**

Technological Advances

Recent technological advancements have significantly reshaped the landscape of SC. The widespread adoption of containerisation technologies like Docker and orchestration tools such as Kubernetes has enabled the creation of scalable, reproducible environments for data analysis. These tools facilitate the seamless packaging and deployment of software environments across different infrastructures, ensuring consistency and efficiency in scientific workflows.

By combining Docker with Kubernetes for container orchestration and Terraform for IaC, we create a seamless environment that automates deployment, scaling, and management across diverse computational ecosystems.

IaC tools, such as Terraform, which acts like a blueprint for IT infrastructure, automates the setup and management of computing resources, making it easier to replicate sophisticated environments, having further streamlined the automation of infrastructure deployment and management. By codifying infrastructure configurations, IaC reduces the complexity and operational overhead traditionally associated with setting up and maintaining IT systems. This automation is particularly valuable in settings with limited IT support, allowing researchers and educators to focus on their core activities rather than managing underlying systems.

Combined with the increasing availability of free or cheap cloud computing resources, these advancements have enabled replicating sophisticated computing facilities in more modest settings. Cloud platforms offer scalable, on-demand access to high-performance computing (HPC) resources, enabling even small institutions to conduct cutting-edge research without the need for substantial capital investment in physical infrastructure.

While the 2020 initiative highlighted the need for more robust cross-research management practices, which this proposal addresses by integrating more IaC, templates, and practical cases for automated deployment.

Building Human Capital and Industry-Academia Synergy

These technological tools are fundamental to the operations of modern, distributed industries worldwide. A solid understanding of these technologies contributes to creating a highly skilled and adaptable workforce and facilitates the seamless transition between academia and industry. This knowledge empowers individuals to move fluidly from academic settings into industrial roles or entrepreneurship and vice versa. **Integrating such technologies into educational and research environments equips students and professionals alike with skills that are in high demand across multiple sectors. It prepares them to navigate the complexities of both scientific research and industrial applications.** For professionals in the private sector, this provides an opportunity to confidently pursue scientific ambitions, knowing they are supported by a robust infrastructure that facilitates both research and advanced training.

By leveraging these advancements, we can foster a dynamic ecosystem that enhances Latin America's scientific and educational capabilities while strengthening the region's position as a competitive player in the global scientific community. This approach supports human capital development, ensuring that students and researchers are well-prepared to contribute meaningfully to both academic and industrial spheres.

Over the long term, this initiative will contribute to a sustainable ecosystem where academia and industry collaborate continuously, driving innovation and regional economic growth. **For instance,** multiple, dozens of programs with multiple ICTP, CERN, and independent programs to tackle data analysis and technical team-work with programs like Physics Without Frontiers, LA-CoNGA Hackathons and Creative Commons Edithatons.

Proposal for Enhanced Open Access Platforms

Multi-User Deployment Strategies

Containerisation and Virtual Machines

Container technologies such as Docker allow for the encapsulation of applications and their dependencies into portable containers that run consistently across different computing environments. Using orchestration tools like Kubernetes, we can manage and scale these containers efficiently, ensuring they meet the computational needs of various scientific experiments.

Virtual machines (VMs) provide another layer of flexibility, enabling the replication of entire operating systems and software environments. This approach can be particularly useful for creating isolated, reproducible environments for data analysis.

Infrastructure as Code

Tools like Terraform, Puppet,... allow for the automated deployment and management of computing resources. By defining infrastructure configurations in code, we can ensure that deployments are consistent, repeatable, and easily scalable. This approach also facilitates version control and collaboration, enabling teams to work together more effectively on infrastructure management.

SaaS for Educational Programmes

Developing SaaS and IaaS platforms that provide access to educational tools and datasets is a key component of this strategy. For example, the ATLAS Open Data project offers Jupyter notebooks, ROOT analysis frameworks, and other resources that can be accessed via web browsers with minimal setup requirements. These platforms can significantly enhance the accessibility and usability of SC resources for educational purposes. And as co-owner of the open access GitHub Organization (<https://github.com/atlas-outreach-data-tools>), we keep building resources even when we are not part of the academia or a traditional research institution.

Integration with Existing Infrastructure

To maximise the impact and accessibility of the mentioned tools, this proposal includes strategies for integrating these new platforms with existing institutional infrastructure. This effort involves working closely with university IT departments and leveraging existing resources to create seamless and efficient workflows between cloud and on-premise IT.

Institutional Partnerships

Building strong partnerships with educational institutions is crucial for the success of this initiative. We will establish pilot programmes in collaboration with selected universities to test and refine the deployment strategies, ensuring they meet the specific needs of different environments. These partnerships will also facilitate the exchange of knowledge and best practices, further enhancing the overall effectiveness of the proposed solutions.

Cloud Service Partnerships

Exploring partnerships with cloud service providers to offer subsidised or free access to computational resources will help minimise that financial constraints do not hinder participation. This is especially important for institutions in resource-limited settings, where access to advanced computing resources can significantly enhance research and educational outcomes.

Security and Data Management

Ensuring the security of data and the reliability of the platforms is paramount. We will implement robust security protocols and data management practices to protect user data and maintain the integrity of the analysis.

Data Security

Adopting industry-standard security practices like encryption, access controls, and regular security audits will help protect sensitive data and maintain user trust. These measures will be integrated into all platform aspects, from data storage and transmission to user authentication and access management.

Data Management and Reproducibility

Implementing best practices for data management, including version control, documentation, and reproducibility protocols, will ensure the reliability and integrity of the research conducted using these platforms. By providing comprehensive documentation and support for these practices, we aim to foster a culture of transparency and reproducibility in scientific research.

The following set of Figures, still valid from 2020 (from 2 to 9), shows how we can use transversal services to homogenise, integrate, reduce costs and improve the quality of scientific research and the researchers.

Figure 2: A simplified view of multiple experiments and the ways they access services and tools in SC and IT, highlighting the area of usage of final services.

This approach of maximising the use of common resources when possible—used in multiple and large collaborations—allows the deployment of generic and eventually economic common infrastructure. Single purchases and/or contracts for various experiments and groups can help optimise the use of funding and obtain more specialised equipment. These platforms could support not only basic science, but projects like climate modeling in the Andes, where robust data processing is crucial for accurate predictions.

Also, in terms of the visibility to possible external funding agencies, it is much more appreciated, especially in multi-country institutions and universities.

Figure 3: A simplified view of multiple experiments and how they can access (final) services and tools in SC and IT using a common Service Provider Platform.

Many of these shared resources are already in place. Open Access, Open Source, Open Data, Open Software and Open Hardware define current and future scientific endeavours. This environment -and legal framework- is beneficial for the long term and fully supports Open “X” projects that we can profit from and contribute to. So, in a first attempt to create a manual guide for researchers in the region, they will already have solid technology and resources planned to be supported for decades.

Figure 4: A simplified view of multiple experiments and the ways they can access services and tools through a common Service Provider Platform in SC and IT, highlighting the area of usage of final services.

Figure 5: A simplified view of multiple experiments and the ways they access services and tools in the areas of SC and IT, highlighting the area of usage of initial-continuous services.

Figure 6: A simplified view of multiple experiments and the ways they can access (initial-continuous) services and tools in the areas of SC and IT using a common Service Provider Platform.

The use of transversal common resources and protocols also allows for doing more. Many of the mentioned resources are free to be used. And with a community that supports their deployment and can assist at any moment.

Because they are used in the industry, we comply with industrial standards. We maintain a high quality of the activities and allow the researchers to gain the know-how that can be relevant to their professional futures inside and outside academia.

Figure 7: A simplified view of multiple experiments and the ways they can access services and tools through a common Service Provider Platform in the areas of SC and IT, highlighting the area of usage of Initial-continuous services.

Figure 8: A simplified view of multiple experiments and the ways they can access services and tools through common Service Provider Platforms in SC and IT, highlighting the area of usage of ALL needed services.

Figure 9: A simplified view of multiple experiments and the ways they can access services and tools through common Service Provider Platforms in SC and IT, highlighting the area of usage of ALL needed services and adding the two main areas to focus on.

In this vision, reproducibility of science through Open Data access is also a relevant (if not the most important) goal. Using services developed on public and/or generic platforms, a new field for capacity building and job/employment creation is easily imaginable.

Implementation Roadmap

Development and Testing

The first phase of implementation will involve designing and testing IaC scripts and container images. We can start with a proof-of-concept deployment, which will serve as a testbed for validating this approach and identifying any potential challenges. This phase will involve close collaboration with IT and research teams to aim that the solutions we develop are robust, scalable, and user-friendly. Commercial and hybrid cloud computing will be involved in that.

Documentation and Training

Developing comprehensive documentation and training materials is essential for supporting educators and IT administrators in deploying and maintaining these resources. We will create step-by-step guides, video tutorials, and online courses to facilitate the adoption and effective use of the proposed solutions. These materials will be designed to cater to users with varying levels of technical expertise, ensuring that the resources are accessible to a broad audience.

Pilot Programmes

We will launch pilot programmes in collaboration with selected universities and research institutions. These programmes will provide valuable feedback on the proposed solutions' effectiveness and usability, helping us refine and improve this approach. The pilot programmes will also serve as case studies to demonstrate the benefits of the SC+IT Hub and build momentum and support for broader adoption. Before the end of the year, we aim to deploy pilot platforms in five universities, focusing on refining IaC templates and container images based on user feedback.

Community Engagement and Support

Building a community of users and contributors is crucial for the success of this initiative. We will establish forums, mailing lists, and regular workshops to foster collaboration and share best practices. By creating a supportive and engaged community, we aim to facilitate the continuous improvement and evolution of the SC+IT Hub, ensuring it remains responsive to its users' needs.

As mentioned before, **using global industrial standards by design, together with education and discipline, will be crucial for maintaining those protocols. It will pay off in the long run—something senior scientists know quite well.**

There is an obvious connection with the region's overall development in the form of the creation of high-aggregated value products, leaving behind the economies of raw materials.

Figure 10: A non-exhausted set of components and resources that help to exemplify the vision of standard services for needs and activities that tend to be generic among different experiments and research activities in the sciences, particularly in physics.

Figure 11: A non-exhausted set of components and resources that help to exemplify the vision of standard services for needs and activities that tend to be generic among different experiments and research activities in the sciences, particularly in physics.

The search for service providers should also be done in regional and local companies and service providers, and the missing ones should be created to boost the integration of multinational projects. This matches the culture and requirements of funding agencies' strategies, like those of the European Union.

Also, encourage the creation and enhancement of resources to make several labs and institutions—at least partially—self-sufficient. These resources could relate to services like food quality control, metrology, and isotope creation for medicine, among others. However, in this proposal, those services can be provided in software and hardware development, quality control, consultancy, industrial assessments, etcetera.

Current and Future Directions

Expanding Data Sources

While our initial focus is on high-energy physics data from ATLAS, we aim to incorporate datasets from other scientific disciplines, broadening the scope and impact of this platform. By providing access to diverse datasets, we can support a wider variety of research and educational initiatives, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and innovation.

Enhancing Data Accessibility

We will explore partnerships with cloud service providers to offer subsidised or free access to computational resources, ensuring that financial constraints do not hinder participation. This approach will help to democratise access to advanced computing tools, enabling more researchers and educators to benefit from these resources.

Continuous Improvement

Our iterative approach will incorporate user feedback and technological advancements to improve the platform continuously. Regular updates and enhancements will be made to seek to the platform remains relevant and effective. We will also establish mechanisms for users to provide feedback and suggest improvements, ensuring that the SC+IT Hub evolves in response to the needs of its community.

Strategic Utilisation of Technological Advancements and Commercial Clouds

Democratising Access to HPC

We will leverage commercial cloud services (e.g., AWS, Google Cloud, Azure) to provide on-demand HPC resources to students and researchers across Latin America. By utilising these platforms, smaller institutions—typically constrained by limited local infrastructure—can access computational power comparable to larger, well-funded organisations. Implementing a pay-as-you-go model will further enhance cost efficiency, making advanced resources more accessible through educational grants or subsidies.

Developing Modular, Scalable Educational Platforms

We aim to create containerised educational environments using Docker or Kubernetes, which can be deployed across various cloud providers. This ensures that students and researchers have consistent access to computational environments, regardless of their location or available resources. Multiple and evolving IaC templates will further automate the deployment of these platforms, simplifying setup and management for educators and tailoring resources to specific courses or research projects.

Enhancing Educational and Training Programmes

Our strategy includes integrating cloud-based computing resources and real-world datasets into university curricula, ensuring that students gain practical experience with industry-relevant tools and technologies. Regular workshops and hackathons will provide additional opportunities for students to develop problem-solving skills using real-world datasets, fostering collaboration between academia and industry professionals. Multiple examples were and are ongoing in several fronts with collaborations with Creative Commons chapters, LA-CoNGA, inait.AI, among others. Including equipment donation that is already on their way.

Collaborative Research and Innovation

We will develop cloud-based platforms to facilitate remote collaboration among researchers across Latin America. These platforms will enable real-time data, code, and computational resource sharing, fostering multi-institutional research efforts. By leveraging open data initiatives, such as the ATLAS Open Data project, we aim to empower researchers with access to high-quality datasets and commercial cloud resources for large-scale analyses.

Sustainability and Scalability

Emphasising sustainable software development practices, we will teach students to write scalable, maintainable code that adapts to evolving technological landscapes. This aligns with broader software sustainability goals, ensuring that the tools and platforms developed remain valuable in the future. Additionally, we will create and distribute multi-user infrastructure deployments tailored to different institutional needs, providing scalability and long-term viability. **The platform is designed to scale horizontally, allowing new institutions to join by replicating existing configurations and leveraging cloud resources.**

Conclusion

This proposal aims to create a robust, scalable, and accessible framework that supports scientific endeavours and capacity-building projects across Latin America. By leveraging modern computing technologies, open-access data, and strategic partnerships with private industry and NGOs, we seek to democratise access to cutting-edge research tools and educational resources. With ongoing workshops and training programmes, both online and in-person, we are actively building local capacity and fostering collaboration. My ultimate goal is to ensure as much as possible that researchers and students in the region can fully participate in and contribute to the global scientific community. We invite more educational institutions, labs, industry partners, and NGOs to join us in this transformative initiative, ensuring that Latin American researchers and students have the tools they need to excel in the global scientific community. **Success will be measured through increased research output and new collaborations, greater student engagement in STEM fields, and successful transitions of students into industry roles.**

Results, examples and new developments are and will be hosted in GitHub organizations:

- <https://github.com/laa-hecap>
- <https://github.com/GOES-training>
- <https://github.com/atlas-outreach-data-tools>

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